

THE THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF MAGNESIUM NITRITE

BY TRAMBAKLAL M. OZA AND N. L. DIPALI

In the study of the mechanism of the reactions taking place in the decomposition of nitrites by heat, magnesium nitrite offers special interest as it decomposes almost completely below 200°, so that the extent of complications due to side reactions coming in at higher temperatures is, with this substance very small. Pure magnesium nitrite has been prepared by a method not used previously in its preparation and the substance has been decomposed under various conditions with a view to affording an insight into the nature of the solid residue at various stages during the course of the decomposition. The gaseous products consist of nitrous anhydride, nitric oxide and nitrogen; the amounts of nitrogen are, at times, quite negligible and at any rate never exceed 2 to 3% in any experiment. The solid residue contains nitrite, nitrate and oxide and its composition tends to the proportion: nitrite used up to nitrate formed to oxide produced as 3 : 1 : 2. The stages involved in the reaction have been clearly brought out.

The thermal decomposition of nitrites was studied by P. C. Ray (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 177), who found the presence of the oxide and the nitrate of the metal, in addition to the undecomposed nitrite, in the residue and nitric oxide, nitrogen peroxide and nitrogen in the gaseous products of the decomposition. The amount of nitrogen peroxide was small, while as regards the relative proportions of nitrogen formed by different nitrites, it is stated that "calcium and magnesium nitrites yielded very little pure nitrogen whereas the barium and sodium salts gave considerable amounts". The following mechanism was assigned to the reactions taking place :

That he was not completely satisfied with the mechanism is significant in the following statement: "as a matter of fact, several reactions go on side by side, some of which, again, probably overlap so that no sharp line of demarcation can be laid down between them". The concluding remarks of the paper are still more significant: "As a result of the purely thermal decomposition, a portion of the salts breaks up into the peroxide and nitric oxide but as the former is unstable, specially under diminished pressure, at the temperature at which the scission takes place, it parts with its oxygen both to the nitric oxide and also to the undecomposed salt in a state of fusion, and that it is in this way that internal oxidation and reduction are brought about". The evidence before the present worker (Oza and Shah, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, 70; Oza, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 173; Oza and Walavalkar, *ibid.*, 1945, 22, 243), as also that brought forward in this paper, is a testimony to exactness of vision and foresight of the great chemist.

In the thermal decomposition of magnesium nitrite, studied by Ray and Ganguli (Ray, *loc. cit.*), the general nature of the reactions was said to be identical with the above.

It was noticed that the decomposition started as early as 60° in vacuum, and further that perceptible amounts of nitrous fumes were seen at the very outset of the experiments. On the basis of their analytical data they concluded that by far the greater proportion of the nitrite decomposed as

but they felt strongly inclined to ascribe the following reaction,

to explain the equivalent amounts of oxide and nitrate in the residue and the appearance of nitrogen in the gas.

Ostwald (*Annalen*, 1914, 403, 32) studied the thermal decomposition of alkali nitrite and advanced the view that nitrogen was formed by the action of nitrogen tetroxide on the fused nitrite as

Oza and Shah (*loc. cit.*) felt inclined to this view but Oza (*loc. cit.*) and Oza and Walavalkar (*loc. cit.*), who undertook a careful study of the thermal decomposition of alkali nitrites at low temperature, at which the intermediate and final stages of Ray's reaction may be largely inoperative, showed that the initial stage, $2 \text{ KNO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{K}_2\text{O} + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2$ (Oza and Shah, *loc. cit.*) was followed by reactions producing nitrogen and the latter was produced by the action of nitric oxide and *not* nitrogen peroxide on the fused nitrite. The following mechanism was ascribed:

It was also shown that the reactions mostly occurred in the molten phase though the possibility of reaction (iv) occurring at the gas-liquid interface was not precluded.

It may be observed that the conclusions of Oza and co-workers differ in two important respects from those of the previous workers, viz., (i) the initial stage as consisting of the dissociation of the nitrite into oxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide and (ii) the formation of nitrogen as dependent on the action of nitric oxide on the fused nitrite, nitrogen peroxide *not* producing nitrogen in contact with the fused nitrite in *one* step. These conclusions have been arrived at by studying the nature and proportion of the gaseous products and the residue at various stages in the course of the decomposition as also by the study of the action of nitric oxide and oxygen on the nitrites in the fused state, the experiments having been conducted near the fusion temperature of the nitrites with a view to eliminating, as far as possible, complications in the reactions. Magnesium nitrite offers, from this point of view, a unique substance as it decomposes at a very low temperature and produces very little nitrogen (Ray and Ganguli, *loc. cit.*), so that the nitrogen-producing reactions are practically absent. This substance was therefore supposed to supply important information on the nature of the stages concerned before the production of nitrogen occurred.

In the present work magnesium nitrite has been prepared by a method not hitherto used in its preparation and the pure substance has been used in experiments in which the nitrite is decomposed under differing conditions of experiment. The gaseous products of the decomposition, as also the solid residue left at the end of each experiment, have been analysed. The results have been found to be very illuminating, as in addition to suggesting the nature of the stages involved, they show that the mechanism may be of quite a universal character in the case of all nitrites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Magnesium Nitrite.—Magnesium nitrite was prepared by Lang (*Svenska Akad. Handl.*, 1860, 3, 14), Hampe (*Annalen*, 1863, 128, 337), Spiegel (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1894, 18, 1423) and P. C. Ray (*loc. cit.*). Various methods were tried by us e.g., double decomposition with equimolecular quantities of silver nitrite and magnesium chloride, followed by evaporation of the filtrate in an air-oven at 50°; the nitrite obtained was of very poor quality containing less than 30% substance; no nitrite was found in the precipitate when ammoniacal solution of the nitrite was used; equimolecular quantities of barium nitrite and magnesium sulphate were dissolved separately in water, mixed and the filtrate dehydrated over P₂O₅. The solid, dried to a constant weight, contained (i) 73.52% and (ii) 73.08% Mg(NO₂)₂, the Mg(NO₂)₂ content of Mg(NO₂)₂, 2H₂O being 76.4%

The method employed by us was that made use of by Ray (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 81, 2031) in the preparation of double nitrites. This enabled us to dispense with the previous step, preparation of pure barium nitrite. Equimolecular quantities of silver nitrite and magnesium chloride were made into a paste in a clean mortar and the extract, which had the deep tint of very concentrated nitrite solutions, was concentrated further to a syrupy state in a P₂O₅ desiccator under partial vacuum and then dried to a constant weight in the desiccator under the ordinary pressure. The substance thus obtained gave on analysis the following results:

(i) 0.0914 g. and 0.0828 g. of the substance gave respectively 0.0712 g. and 0.0642 g. MgSO₄ (Treadwell and Hall, Vol. II, 6th Ed., p. 76). [Found: Mg, 0.01438 g. and 0.01297 g. i.e., 15.74% and 15.66% respectively. Calc. for Mg(NO₂)₂, 2H₂O: Mg, 15.98%].

(ii) 0.0396 g. and 0.0414 g. of the substance consumed 10.65 c.c. and 11.15 c.c. of 0.09709N-KMnO₄ respectively. [Found: Mg(NO₂)₂, 0.0308 g. and 0.03148 g. i.e., 75.95% and 76.03% respectively. Calc. for Mg(NO₂)₂, 2H₂O: Mg(NO₂)₂, 76.4%]. Ray (*loc. cit.*) observed that the stable variety of magnesium nitrite contained two molecules of water of crystallisation.

Apparatus and Procedure.—The apparatus consisted of a tube, A, closed at one end and fitted with a ground-in-glass joint at the other through which it was connected to a bubbler, B, through another ground-in-glass joint. The bubbler was connected through another ground-in-glass joint to the sprengel and hyvac pumps.

A weighed quantity of magnesium nitrite was taken in A and about 2 c.c. of a freshly made, concentrated solution of potassium hydroxide was placed in B. The apparatus was set up with a coating of vacuum grease on all the joints and taps and then evacuated with the hyvac pump. The apparatus was tested for leaks by allowing it to stand for a few hours, and if vacuum-tight, the Sprengel pump was worked with its characteristic clicks for half an hour before the start of an experiment.

An oil-bath was heated outside to the temperature of the experiment and then inserted below A. Temperature was maintained to within about $\pm 2^\circ$ by regulating the flame under the bath. After the heating for the stipulated time was over, the bath was removed and the gases were pumped off into eudiometers and kept aside for analysis. The residue in A was dissolved out in distilled water and made to 100 c.c. in a measuring flask and subsequently examined for its nitrite and nitrate content. The alkali in B was also made to 100 c.c. and was examined for nitrite alone as the gas was found to contain always a large excess of free nitric oxide, and the alkali was therefore not likely to contain any nitrate.

Analysis of Gaseous products and Residues.—The gas, measured out at the room temperature and pressure, was absorbed in alkaline sodium sulphite, the end of the absorption being tested with acidified ferrous sulphate. The residual gas was taken as nitrogen. All volumes, recorded in the tables, are at N.T.P.

For determining nitrous anhydride, the alkali solution (25 c.c.) was treated with 10 c.c. of 0.025 N - $KMnO_4$ solution to which dilute sulphuric acid was then added.

TABLE I

Heating a fixed mass of magnesium nitrite at various temperatures for 30 mins.

1 Expt. No.	2		3 Wt. anhyd. $Mg(NO_2)_2$ corresp. to column 2.	4 Temp.	5 Composition of gaseous products.			
	Wt. $Mg(NO_2)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ taken.				Total.	N_2O_3 .	NO.	N_2
1	0.2486 g.		0.1898 g.	110°	6.4 c.c.	0.85 c.c.	5.45 c.c.	0.1 c.c.
2	0.2498		0.1907	130°	43.85	1.8	41.25	0.8
3	0.2474		0.1891	150°	46.05	2.3	42.85	0.9
4	0.2460		0.1878	170°	44.86	1.65	42.51	0.7
5	0.2744		0.2095	190°	46.97	2.01	44.20	0.8
6 Composition of the residue.			7	8 Composition in g. mols				9 Ratio $NO_2^+ : NO_3^+ : O^+$.
Nitrite.	Nitrate.	Oxide (calc.)		$Mg(NO_2)_2$ used up.	Nitrite used up.	Nitrate produced.	Oxide formed.	
0.1515 g.	0.0238 g.	0.005813 g.	0.0383 g.	3.3×10^{-4}	1.6×10^{-4}	1.68×10^{-4}	2 : 1 : 1	
0.01483	0.06937	0.04222	0.1758	1.5×10^{-3}	0.469×10^{-3}	1.05×10^{-3}	3 : 1 : 2	
0.01164	0.06476	0.04403	0.1774	1.52×10^{-3}	0.435×10^{-3}	1.09×10^{-3}		
0.00868	0.06648	0.04414	0.1791	1.6×10^{-3}	0.589×10^{-3}	1.03×10^{-3}		
0.01008	0.08586	0.04568	0.1995	1.7×10^{-3}	0.578×10^{-3}	1.14×10^{-3}	3 : 1 : 2	

The mixture was well shaken and heated to about 70° . The excess of the permanganate was then reduced by adding a known volume of a standard (0.025 *N*) tetroxalate solution and the excess of the latter was then titrated back with the standard KMnO_4 solution.

Nitrite in the solid residue was determined in the manner detailed above with the difference that 0.1 *N* solutions were used. For determining nitrate in the residue, the nitrite present was first oxidised to nitrate by adding the requisite amount of standard KMnO_4 (0.1 *N*) solution and the total nitrate then determined by the ferrous sulphate method (Cumming and Kay, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 6th Ed., pp. 100-101). The magnesium oxide, present in the residue, was worked out by subtracting the magnesium equivalent of magnesium nitrite and magnesium nitrate found from that of the magnesium nitrite taken at the start of the experiment.

Table I contains the results of experiments carried out with a fixed mass of magnesium nitrite, heated at different fixed temperatures for a fixed period of time. The results show that (i) nitrogen trioxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen are, all, produced at all temperatures between 110° and 190° ; (ii) the amount of nitrogen is very small at 110° and its amount is not more than 2.5% of the total gas even at 190° ; the proportion of nitrous anhydride, N_2O_3 , is at low temperatures (110°) as high as 13% but diminishes rapidly with rise of temperature; nitric oxide is the main gaseous product of the decomposition, its proportion being normally not less than 80%; (iii) magnesium oxide and magnesium nitrate are always present along with magnesium nitrite in all experiments, and it appears peculiar that the amount of decomposition, in half-an-hour, is the same at 130° and at 190° , although at the latter temperature the rate of the decomposition is much greater showing that beyond a certain stage appreciable amounts of the nitrite do not apparently decompose: the amounts of it formed and decomposed, in a given unit or interval of time, may not be very much different from each other; (iv) in all the experiments except the first, wherein the extent of the decomposition is but slight, the proportions of nitrite used up to nitrate produced, to oxide formed, are approximately as 3:1:2; in the first experiment these are as 2:1:1.

TABLE II

Effect of time on the decomposition of a fixed mass of magnesium nitrite, heated at 110° .

Expt No.	1	2	3	4	5		
					Composition of gaseous products.		
	Wt. of $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_2)_2$, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ taken.	Wt. anhyd. $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_2)_2$ corresp. to column 2.	Time.	Total.	N_2O_3 .	NO.	N_2 .
1	0.2486 g.	0.1898 g.	30 min.	6.4 c.c.	0.85 c.c.	5.45 c.c.	0.1 c.c.
2	0.2528	0.1930	60	21.22	0.88	19.5	0.84
3	0.2442	0.1864	90	22.15	1.55	20.2	0.4
4	0.2678	0.2046	90	22.3	1.3	20.6	0.4
5	0.2530	0.1932	120	25.3	0.9	24.2	0.2
6	0.2712	0.2071	120	25.1	1.1	23.5	0.5

TABLE II (contd.)

6 Composition of the residue			7	8 Composition in g. mols.			9 Ratio
Nitrite.	Nitrate.	Oxide (enc.).	Mg (NO ₂) ₂ used up.	Nitrite used up.	Nitrate produced.	Oxide formed.	NO ₂ ' : NO ₃ ' : O ^o .
0.1515 g	0.0238 g	0.005813 g.	0.0383 g.	3.3×10^{-4}	1.6×10^{-1}	1.68×10^{-1}	2 : 1 : 1
0.09550	0.04 0	0.02221	0.0975	8.4×10^{-4}	4.0×10^{-1}	5.5×10^{-4}	
0.08429	0.0502	0.02183	0.1021	8.6×10^{-4}	3.4×10^{-1}	5.4×10^{-4}	2.5 : 1 : 1.5
0.09718	0.0540	0.02227	0.1074	9.2×10^{-4}	3.7×10^{-1}	5.57×10^{-4}	2.5 : 1 : 1.5
0.08123	0.0536	0.02433	0.1120	9.6×10^{-4}	3.6×10^{-1}	5.7×10^{-4}	2.5 : 1 : 1.5
0.09361	0.0525	0.02493	0.1135	9.78×10^{-4}	3.54×10^{-1}	5.8×10^{-4}	

Table II contains results of the experiments with a fixed mass of magnesium nitrite, heated at 110° for varying periods of time. It may be observed in these results that the effect of time is not so great between 60 and 90 minutes or between 60 and 120 minutes as between 30 and 60 minutes, showing again, as before, that beyond a certain stage the net amount of magnesium nitrite apparently decomposing is very small. The results in Table II show further that (i) nitrous anhydride, nitric oxide and nitrogen are all present in the gaseous products of the decomposition, the amount of nitrogen present being never greater than 1 to 2%; the proportion of nitric oxide present is large and compares favourably with that in the preceding table; the amounts of nitrous anhydride do not increase proportionately with time, being practically the same in 30 as in 120 minutes; (ii) as in the preceding set of experiments, magnesium oxide and magnesium nitrate are both present in the residue along with magnesium nitrite; the proportion of magnesium nitrite used up to magnesium nitrate formed, to magnesium oxide produced is approximately as 2.5 : 1 : 1.5 and a tendency is visible for these proportions to become as 3 : 1 : 2; (iii) as before, the net quantity of magnesium nitrite decomposing in experiments of longer duration are comparatively small with respect to those in experiments of shorter duration.

Results of the experiments on the effect of variation of mass of magnesium nitrite at a constant temperature (110°), heated for a fixed interval of time (30 mins.) are recorded in Table III. These results show that (i) practically no nitrogen is present, almost all the gas consisting of nitrous anhydride and nitric oxide; amounts of nitrous anhydride, though small, are much larger than those in the preceding tables and fluctuate, the proportion being as large as 16% with 0.62 g. of magnesium nitrite. This observation, along with the corresponding observations made in Tables I and II, shows that (i) the presence of nitrous anhydride in the gas is due mainly to the small portion which escapes the sphere of reaction at the commencement of the experiment; (ii) the effect of increasing mass is to increase the amount of the decomposition, in almost a regular manner; (iii) as usual, magnesium oxide and magnesium nitrate are both present in the residue along with magnesium nitrite; the proportion of magnesium nitrate is, it must be particularly observed, very small in the first experiment and the proportions of magnesium nitrite used up and magnesium oxide formed are approximately equal to each other. With increase in mass, the proportions of magnesium oxide and magnesium nitrate tend to become identical and the proportion of magnesium nitrite used up

TABLE III

Effect of mass on the decomposition of magnesium nitrite at 110° for 30 mins.

Expt. No.	2	3	4	5		
				Composition of gaseous products:		
1	Mg(NO ₂) ₂ , 2H ₂ O taken	Anhydrous Mg(NO ₂) ₂ corresp. to column 2.	Total gas.	N ₂ O ₂	NO	N ₂
1	0.1248 g.	0.09526 g.	2.45 c.c.	0.36 c.c.	2.06 c.c.	Trace
2	0.2486	0.1848 g.	6.4	0.85	5.45	0.1 c.c.
3	0.3780	0.2885	9.2	0.98	8.21	Trace
4	0.5002	0.3849	15.42	2.1	13.2	0.12
5	0.5116	0.3007	15.39	1.86	13.2	0.3
6	0.6270	0.4782	20.2	3.2	16.55	0.4

6			7	8			9
Composition of the residue:			Mg(NO ₂) ₂ used up.	Composition in g. mols.			Ratio. NO ₂ : NO ₂ : O ₂
Nitrite.	Nitrate.	Oxide (calc.)		Nitrite used up.	Nitrate produced.	Oxide formed.	
0.07603 g.	0.0038 g.	0.002877 g.	0.01923 g.	1.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	6:1:5
0.1515	0.0238	0.005813	0.0393	3.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	2:1:1
0.2211	0.0456	0.01109	0.0574	6.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	2:1:1
0.2795	0.0514	0.01924	0.1024	9.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.9 × 10 ⁻⁴	2:1:1
0.2880	0.0675	0.01714	0.1027	9.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.56 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	2:1:1
0.3509	0.0802	0.01951	0.1183	10.2 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.42 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.77 × 10 ⁻⁴	

becomes almost twice as great as that of the nitrate formed or oxide produced; (iv) magnesium nitrite and nitric oxide are both present amongst the products, in all these experiments, in plentiful amounts and still no nitrogen is found in the gas.

The outstanding fact about all these experimental results is that in all cases where the decomposition has reached a steady state, the proportions of magnesium nitrite used up to magnesium nitrate formed, to magnesium oxide produced are, as nearly as possible, 3:1:2, while in other cases where the decomposition has presumably not reached such a state, the proportions are fluctuating and may be 2.5:1:1.5 or 2:1:1 or some such as these. In any case, there is significantly a distinct tendency for the latter figures to pass into the former (Table II).

DISCUSSION

The results in Tables I, II and III show that magnesium nitrite dissociates in the initial stage as

This is soon followed by the reaction between the produced nitrogen tetroxide (of the nitrous anhydride: nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide being produced in equivalent amounts) and the unchanged nitrite in the decomposing mass as

and, to a very meagre extent, by the reaction

The extent of the reaction (iii), though very trifling, seems to depend upon temperature.

As magnesium oxide begins to be formed and accumulate in the residual mass, a reaction seems to come into being consuming a portion of the oxide and producing, in the process, equivalent amounts of magnesium nitrite and magnesium nitrate, as

Reaction (iv) is very prominent in the later stages when the proportion of free magnesium oxide present in the residuc is considerable.

The fact that nitrogen is almost entirely absent in all experiments at 110°, even when the extent of the decomposition is fairly appreciable, shows that nitrogen is not produced in the initial stage. This fact, taken together with the fact that nitrous anhydride is present in all experiments, favours the view that the initial stage in the decomposition of magnesium nitrite consists, as in the case of alkali nitrites (Oza, *loc. cit.*), of the dissociation of the nitrite as

This equation requirs that nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide should be present in equivalent amounts. In practice, this is never found and in view of the well known properties of nitrogen tetroxide, it can hardly be expected. Nitrogen is known to be a very strong oxidising agent and reacts at ordinary temperatures, and even at temperatures at and below zero very vigorously with all substances with which it comes into contact. Its slight appearance in these experiments must therefore be ascribed not to its less than 100% activity but to its escape, immediately after formation, into the highly vacuous space above by distension rendered possible by the comparatively low activity of magnesium nitrite and by the absence of magnesium oxide in the sphere of its influence, viz., the decomposing mass. The facts that (i) the proportion of nitrous anhydride is much greater in half hour experiments than in experiments of greater duration and (ii) the proportion of nitrous anhydride is almost the same in all experiments in Tables I and II, and (iii) the proportion of nitrous anhydride depends upon the mass of the nitrite undergoing the decomposition, being greater with greater mass, provide evidence in favour of the conception. It is thus evident that the nitrogen peroxide reacts, immediately after its formation, in a manner which produces nitric oxide, the gas found in large amounts in the gaseous products, but not nitrogen. Under the conditions of the experiments this would occur as in the reaction (ii).

It is also evident that the reaction (ii) follows reaction (i) and is not simultaneous with the latter; the comparatively very low value of nitrate in the first of the mass experiments (Table III) is an evidence in favour of this view.

Another side reaction bringing about the consumption of the nitrogen tetroxide seems to set in as soon as magnesium oxide is produced in the decomposing mass. The very nature of it requires that it cannot set in before the reaction (i) and, that, it sets in, though to a very limited extent, as soon as the decomposition begins, i.e., as soon as magnesium oxide is produced in the reacting mass. Magnesium oxide seems to fix up nitrogen peroxide (or tetroxide) quite effectively and practically none of the tetroxide can escape unreacted if magnesium oxide is present in the residue in sufficient amounts. The observation that the amount of nitrogen tetroxide in the gas is large in all half-hour experiments at 110° seems dependent on two factors, viz lack of magne-

sium oxide in the decomposing mass at the start of the experiments and distension of some of the gas in the vacuum prevailing in the system at the commencement of the experiments.

With a view to obtaining a more correct idea of the role of magnesium oxide in the decomposition, an experiment was performed in which about 20% (on the weight of magnesium nitrite taken) magnesium oxide was admixed with the magnesium nitrite. The heating was done for half an hour at 130°. The results of this experiment are given below and show that free nitrous anhydride is present in the gas to a much smaller extent (cf. expt. 2, Table I). It should be noticed also that the decomposition is retarded by the presence of magnesium oxide, a product of the decomposition or dissociation in the system and this observation is interesting as it lends evidence to the reversible nature of the commencing stage as shown in equation (i) above. Note may also be taken of the facts that (a) the amount and proportion of nitrogen in the gas is much less in this experiment than in the corresponding experiment of the temperature series; (b) the amounts of magnesium nitrite used up to magnesium nitrate formed, to magnesium oxide produced are almost strictly in the ratio of 3:1:2. This shows that when conditions become favourable for the complete consumption of all the nitrogen tetroxide of the nitrous anhydride, disengaged in the decomposition, the solid residue is likely to show the amount of magnesium nitrite (used up) to magnesium nitrate formed to magnesium oxide produced in the ratio of 3:1:2.

Mg(NO ₂) ₂ , 2H ₂ O taken.	Wt. Mg(NO ₂) ₂ + MgO taken.	Anhydrous Mg. (NO ₂) ₂ .	Total.	Composition of the gaseous products:			
				N ₂ O ₂ .	NO.	N ₂ .	
0.2616 g.	0.3270 g.	0.1998 g.	34.4 c.c.	1.24 c.c.	32.9 c.c.	0.25 c.c.	
Residue: Composition		Mag. nitrite	Composition in g. mols.				
Nitrite.	Nitrate formed.	Oxide produced.	used up.	Nitrite used up.	Nitrate formed.	Oxide produced.	Ratio NO ₂ :NO ₂ :O ₂ .
0.04391 g.	0.06547 g.	0.03607 g.	0.1599 g.	13.44 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.42 × 10 ⁻⁴	9.026 × 10 ⁻⁴	3:1:2

Nitrogen peroxide will react with magnesium oxide evidently as

producing equivalent quantities of the nitrite and the nitrate. The extents to which the reactions (ii) and (iii) occur, depend on the nature of the decomposing mass and on the conditions, viz., temperature, mass, etc., prevailing in the experiment. It is this production and consumption of magnesium oxide and magnesium nitrite, during the course of the decomposition, which modify the relative amounts of magnesium nitrite, magnesium oxide and magnesium nitrate observed, and account for the fluctuations in the amounts of these substances observed in the experiments.

It is now possible to account for the relative proportions, 3:1:2, of the magnesium nitrite used up to magnesium nitrate formed, to magnesium oxide produced, found in all the experiments which have run to completion and also to account for the pro-

portions, other than these, observed in the experiments recorded in Tables I, II and III. The initial stage, represented by the equation (i), is modified, in the commencing stages of the decomposition, mainly by the reaction put down in the equation (ii), in the intermediate stages of the decomposition, mainly by the reactions represented by the equations (ii) and (iii), and in the end stages of the decomposition, mainly by the reaction represented by the equation (iii). It can be readily shown that the different stages acting cumulatively, will produce the result represented by the equation,

Thus, in the commencing stages :

in the intermediate stages :

in the end stages :

The experimental results show that nitrogen is produced in all the experiments without exception. The proportion of nitrogen, though very small, is found to depend upon the temperature of the experiment and it is evident that it is produced as the result of a reaction that is going on concurrently with the others. As its proportion is very small, it cannot affect, to any appreciable extent, the course of the main reactions under the conditions of the experiments.

Although the temperature used in these experiments precludes the possibility of reduction of nitric oxide, the production of nitrogen must, at any rate, be ascribed to the reaction,

(cf. Oza, *loc. cit.* Oza and Walavalkar, *loc. cit.*). This is readily understood when it is remembered that the extent of a reaction is conditioned also by the *state* of the reacting molecules and that Maxwellian distribution renders it probable that, at any temperature, a certain fraction of the reacting molecules. the fraction may be very small. may by deriving energy from the molecules with which they happen to collide, become excited and capable of reacting.

To account for the occurrence of nitrogen Ray and Ganguli (*loc. cit.*) suggested the reaction,

and this equation had, from their point of view, the additional merit that it accounted for the equivalent amounts of magnesium nitrate and magnesium oxide observed by them in their residue. They were, however, disinclined to ascribe the equation to the mechanism as the amount of nitrogen observed by them did not agree with its requirements. They therefore put forward the equation,

which is the same as the equation (v), given above. From their point of view, this equation had, on the other hand, the defect that it did not account for the production of nitrogen and for the occurrence of equivalent amounts of nitrate and oxide found by them in the residue of their experiment.

The present work shows that their observation on the equivalence of magnesium nitrate and magnesium oxide in the residue is only incidental or casual (*vide expts.* in Table III and Expt. 1, Table I). It is not possible to account for the quantity of nitrogen observed by them in their experiment. The present work shows that the amount of nitrogen never exceeds 2.5% and therefore the 12.5% found by them, cannot be explained except on the assumption that their operative temperature might have been higher. With the temperatures used by us (up to 190°), the proportion has not been found to exceed 2.5%; to be sure of this fact, an experiment was performed in which about 0.5 g. of magnesium nitrite was heated at 130° (their temperature was 120°) till about 100 c.c. gas was given off. Analysis of this gas too showed the presence of only 2.0 c.c. nitrogen in the total of 93.8 c.c. which contained, in addition, 89.0 c.c. nitric oxide and 2.8 c.c. nitrous anhydride.

The way in which the production of nitrogen will modify the relative proportions of magnesium nitrite used up to magnesium nitrate formed, to magnesium oxide produced, may be demonstrated by equations in an arbitrary case :

The volume of nitrogen, as shown in this last equation, is one-sixth of that of nitric oxide and the proportions of the nitrite used up to the nitrate formed, to the oxide produced are, roughly as 2:1:1.

THE M. R. SCIENCE INSTITUTE,
GUJARAT COLLEGE, AHMEDABAD
AND
THE KARNATAK COLLEGE, DEHRWAR.

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